

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN

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In our country, a number of reforms are being carried out to create a favorable entrepreneurial environment, increase the legal freedom of businessmen, especially in the development of family entrepreneurship. And entrepreneurial activity is becoming a leading sector of our economy.

Today, most of the population of the countries of the world suffers from the problem of unemployment. In order to avoid this problem in our country, the government has granted wide freedoms for small businesses and private businesses. 76% of the able-bodied population is employed in this area. In the further development of this sphere, the issue of wider promotion of the concept of entrepreneurship among the population is becoming very important.

Today, family business is the most popular type of entrepreneurship in the world. In particular, the number of family firms in the USA is 15,0 mln. ni will organize. In Sweden, 60.0% of the able-bodied population is occupied by family entrepreneurship. Family tad, according to experts from the London School of Economics

Famous Russian economist V.Afanasev assessed family business as "the foundation for easing social tension and democratizing market relations, the formation of the middle class."

The socio-economic policy pursued in Uzbekistan includes a wide range of issues. Additional guarantees were provided for the systematic increase in incomes of the population, the formation of employment and Labor Relations, Social Protection and support of certain categories of the population, including entrepreneurs and farm women.

In particular, the practice of granting preferential loans was established in order to ensure the employment of women and their wide involvement in entrepreneurial activity.

Commercial banks account for more than 30% of micro-credit base customers as women. At the expense of commercial banks, more than 172 thousand women receive loans in the amount of 4.9 trillion soums

Positive qualities of being an entrepreneur

- The entrepreneur constantly acts independently in the implementation of his activities. It develops and implements new and innovative ideas on the basis of freedom
- Can make a huge contribution to the development of the country.
- The decision is made by himself and can be made by himself.
- An entrepreneur can create jobs for others.
- The feeling of satisfaction with what he has done serves as the most necessary motive for him.
- An entrepreneur with high intellectual potential will be able to introduce modern technologies and develop products that replace imports.
- It is considered to have tremendous opportunities in self-development.

The main tasks of the Joint-Stock Commercial people's Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the introduction of the position of deputy head of the branch of the district (city) for the support of women and family entrepreneurship are as follows:

- In the provision of loans through a single electronic platform of programs for the development of family entrepreneurship, it is studied by the assistant governor on the spot where goods and services are actually delivered (provided), ensuring the allocation of loan funds within a period of one day after the approval of the borrower electronically;

- Programs for the development of family entrepreneurship and women's

- to control the targeted use of preferential loans allocated at the expense of resource funds of the support fund, timely qualitative conduct of preliminary, current, targeted and annual monitoring;

- Plan established within the framework of programs for the development of family entrepreneurship-ensuring the timely implementation of graphs within the specified period;

- The programs for the development of family entrepreneurship and the fund for the support of women develop measures to constantly analyze and control and collect the part of preferential loans allocated at the expense of the resource, which has become a problem. According to social programs aimed at the development of family entrepreneurship, for 2022, more than 94 thousand women-girls

received \$ 1.7 billion. more than sum benefits loans have been allocated and more than 93,000 new jobs have been created.

There are indeed many advantages of a family business. Including he:

- Categories of the population that are not used by employers in most cases make it possible to use the labor of pensioners, student youth, disabled people;
- Collective creativity of participants in family entrepreneurship- Serves to stabilize the socio-situation in society, forms a practical future-oriented environment.

1 picture. Positive aspects of being an entrepreneur .

There are also positive aspects of being an entrepreneur, about which are formulated in Figure 1.

Today, the majority of our compatriots who have established a family business in our country and are following this, both in marriage and in love with our society. It is even more remarkable that the number of agricultural sectors, in particular those that organize their family business on the basis of agriculture, livestock, fishing, beekeeping and crafts, trade and services, is increasing. According to the data provided by the " Mahalla "charitable foundation, there are more than 4 million apartments and about 10,000 neighborhood and rural citizens' gatherings across the country.

As you know, one of the most common forms of democracy is the bodies of self - government of citizens. The main link of such a system in Uzbekistan is formed by neighborhoods that have an incomparable place in society. It is this neighborhood

- In the neighborhoods there is currently practically this system, and as a logical continuation, such centers that promote family business and entrepreneurship are the first to open up the entrepreneurial and business potential of the neighborhood's population, aimed at its realization and further development.

- To provide business knowledge necessary for the effective conduct of business activities, including consultations on marketing, management, financial planning, etc., to familiarize businessmen with the legal and regulatory documents necessary for their activities and to provide practical assistance in their application, to assist entrepreneurs and businessmen in the protection of their rights, as well as to provide professors and researchers on the one hand

- E such centers in neighborhoods address the following main issues

- To provide information on the conditions and benefits created to support entrepreneurship in our country among the residents of the neighborhood;

- To issue a consultation on state registration, filling out official documents and submitting reports for those wishing to start their work;

- To start their own business among the population and promote entrepreneurship and stimulation;

- Provide practical assistance in solving the problems faced by entrepreneurs;

- Increase legal and professional literacy of entrepreneurs;

- Popularization and development of self-employment;

- Further popularization and development of family business;

- Assistance in solving the employment issue;

- Increase the tax base for the country's budget;

-To create an opportunity for professors and teachers, as well as researcher and student youth to apply their knowledge in practice;

Summing up from the above points, we can say that such centers of consultation

In neighborhoods, people's views on Business and entrepreneurship and opinions change for the better. They have a desire to engage in entrepreneurial activity. This counseling center will become the most convenient and reliable supportive link for people to engage in entrepreneurship and family business.

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